

Influencing Organizational Performance Through High Performance Work System and Employee Engagement- Exploring the Moderation of Task Proficiency

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Abstract

This study aimed to explore the influence of High-Performance Work System (HPWS) and Employee Engagement (EE) on Perceived Organizational Performance (POP), while also examining the moderating role of Employee Task Proficiency (ETP). Structural equation modeling approach was employed to analyze data using SmartPLS version 3.9. A total of 147 responses were collected through non-probability purposive sampling. The results indicated that HPWS and ETP positively influenced POP, the moderation of ETP and EE was found to significantly influence POP. Adversely, ETP does not have any moderation between HPWS and POP. These findings suggest that organizations can enhance their perceived performance by implementing effective HPWS practices and nurturing employee task proficiency and engagement.

Keywords: High-Performance Work System (HPWS), Employee Engagement (EE), Perceived Organizational Performance (POP), Task Proficiency (ETP), Moderation, Structural equation modeling (SEM)

Introduction

Organizational performance is a significant area of interest for scholars and managers since it impacts a firm's profitability, competitiveness, and sustainability in today's volatile business climate (Nader et al., 2022). Organizations frequently re-engineer and implement several internal factors and practices to improve their performance, such as HRM practices. Since human resource (HR) managers prove their active and indispensable existence in an organization, their contribution through developing and implementing diverse work practices, policies, and procedures that impact the visual and direct organizational performance (Mahapatro, 2021, p. 5-20). In recent years, HR practitioners and scholars have empirically demonstrated the impact of HR responsibilities on the complex field of organizations' performance, regardless of their size or industry orientations. (Otoo, 2019; Paul and Anantharaman, 2020).

Many studies, both new and old, have shown that HRM improves organizational performance. However, this relationship needs more research because the costs of applying HRM practices change over time. In different countries, organizations, cultures, and industries, HRM functions are used in different ways, which in turn affects how well

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companies do (Keramatiyazdi et al., 2023; Tensay and Sing, 2020). Besides addressing Black-box issues of HRM practices and organizational performance studies, Tensay and Sing, (2020) introduced the mediating impact of employee engagement in the relationship between HRM functions and organizational relationships but eventually assumed the direct effect of employee engagement and suggested further research avenues. Additionally, Al-Ajlouni, (2021) mentioned that studying the impact of an isolated single HRM practice on organizational performance metrics has less significance. Furthermore, Keramatiyazdi et al., (2023) anticipated the existence of a moderator variable after having a positive relation between high-performance work systems and operational performance in the Iranian management field.

Though many prior investigations have separately evaluated the impact of HPWS and Employee Engagement on Perceived Organizational Performance (POP), the association of High-Performance Work Systems (HPWS) and Employee Engagement (EE) in a single framework for explaining Perceived Organizational Performance (POP) is less frequently studied. (Park and Ryu, 2023; Ashiru et al., Keramatiyazdi et al., 2023; 2022; Yadav et al., 2022; Dorta-Afonso et al., 2021; Ogbonnaya and Aryee, 2021; Ahmed et al., 2020; Otoo, 2019; Otieno et al., 2015; Ruanggoon, 2015). Moreover, Task Proficiency (ETP) has received comparatively less attention from researchers for unveiling its moderating impact on perceived organizational performance, but its influence on creative behavior, organizations' creative actions, employee engagement, and commitment is available (El-Kassar et al., 2022; Boon and Kalshoven, 2014).

Considering the aforementioned research suggestions and directions, this study has excelled in the following contributions. First, this study looks at how HPWS affects the performance of an organization by including a set of HRM actions in its overall concept. Second, employee engagement is considered a direct construct that has an impact on organizational performance. Next, researchers have studied the influences of HPWS, employee engagement, and employee task proficiency on organizational performance. Eventually, moderating effects of employee task proficiency on employee engagement to organizational performance, and HPWS to organizational performance have been unleashed. Moreover, considering the importance of studying the tertiary-level education industry of Bangladesh mentioned by Shahriar et al., (2021), this research attempts to explore the organizational performance of private universities of Bangladesh.

HPWS is a comprehensive and integrated collection of human resource practices designed to boost corporate efficiency by improving employee skills, motivation, and engagement (Jewell et al., 2022). Selective personnel, comprehensive training and development, performance-based compensation, and employee involvement are common practices in these systems (Lin et al., 2022). Conversely, Employee Engagement (EE) is the employee's emotional and intellectual commitment to their organization, which leads to discretionary effort and improved job performance (Rehman et al., 2022). HPWS and employee engagement (EE) have enhanced perceived organizational performance (POP) by increasing employee motivation, commitment to the institution, overall productivity, and job performance, which consequently ensures superior and cutting-edge business operations in an industry (Ashiru et al., 2022; Lubis, 2022; Ahmed et al., 2020; Tensay and Sing, 2020; Ahmed et al., 2018; Ruanggoon, 2015). The combined HPWS techniques

and employee engagement foster a synergistic impact that supports corporate success. (Al-Ajlouni, 2021).

Each person and institution in the tertiary education industry makes small but important contributions to the development and creation of human capital that keep a country's economy growing and its people getting better lives (Marchiori et al., 2022; Adedeji & Campbell, 2013; Mubashiru et al., 2016; Alam & Parvin, 2017). Considering the contributions of the higher education industry, the government of Bangladesh enacted the Private University Act in 2010 whereas the foundation of private universities was encouraged in 1992. Though private universities in Bangladesh have witnessed constant growth in numbers and size since the inception of the first private university in the final decade of the last century to accommodate the increasing number of students, their performance in terms of quality education has always been controversial (Shahriar et al., 2021; Mazumder, 2014). Furthermore, a substantial body of research supports the notion that effective human resource management (HRM) practices, such as performance management, training and development, and employee recognition, significantly contribute to employee well-being, job satisfaction, and performance, ultimately leading to improved organizational performance. The strategic alignment of HRM techniques with organizational goals and the focus on fostering a positive work environment can enhance institutional outcomes (Ogbonnaya and Aryee. 2021). Under such context, the performance of educational institutions and the engagement of its human resources are studied in this report. Sometimes, a high-performance work system has a mediating role in the relationship of HR practices to employee performance (Abugre and Nasere, 2020). Employee engagement and commitment have a remarkable synergic influence on organizational productivity and performance when combined with HR practices (Patro, 2013; Otieno et al., 2015; Đorđević et al., 2020). Furthermore, employee task efficiency and independence resulted in swelling employees' commitment, engagement, satisfaction in work, and organizational loyalty (Zanabazar & Jigjiddorj, 2022; Boon & Kalshoven, 2014).

This study attempts to draw an impactful relationship between HPWS, employee engagement, employee task proficiency, and perceived organizational performance in the Bangladeshi private university industry. Though this study has been concentrated on the tertiary education sector, researchers have a chance to extend their efforts toward diversified manufacturing and service industries of many developing and underdeveloped countries on different continents.

Literature Review: Prior Research and Hypotheses Development

Theoretical Framework: Resource-Based View (RBV) theory and Human Capital Theory (HCT).

The resource-based view (RBV) theory addresses the heterogeneity of resource possession that generates differences in the performance of organizations in a specific industry. The RBV theory proclaims an organization can establish a prominent competitive edge in a market by wisely developing and leveraging unique internal resources. According to Lubis (2022), Ahmed et al. (2018), and Doove et al. (2014), an organization can establish a prominent competitive edge in a market by wisely

developing and leveraging unique internal resources. Organizational performance has been a popular metric for denoting competitive advantage in a resource-based view model (Salsabila et al., 2022; Lubis, 2022; Ahmed et al., 2018; Doove et al., 2014). Besides, Ruangoon (2015) studied human capital, organizational culture, and high-performance work systems as prime determinants of the resource-based view and explained the relationship between organizational performance and the stated determinants of the resource-based view. Consequently, this paper has accommodated perceived organizational performance (POP) and high-performance work systems (HPWS) under a resource-based view theory.

Researchers also pointed to employees as key stakeholders and the necessity to engage employees in the operational process for effective organizational performance (Graham et al., 2023). In addition, Song et al. (2018) empirically showed that highly work-involved employees controlled organizational performance in a resource-based view (RBV) approach. Hence, employee engagement (EE) has been purposefully listed in the current research model to explain perceived organizational performance (POP).

Human capital theory (HCT) acknowledges that human productivity is renewable because the productive capacity of human beings can be sharpened and excelled through continuous education, training, experiences, and skills. Hence, human capital theory is frequently used to explain organizational performance (Wuttaphan, 2017). Employee task proficiency measures how an employee completes his assignment and duties, complying with the required standards that directly indicate an employee's productive capacity. As a result, in this study employee task proficiency (ETP) is framed in the model to explain perceived organizational performance (POP).

Figure 1: Research Model

Employee Engagement (EE) and Perceive Organizational Performance (POP)

Recent research has consistently found a link between EE and POP. According to Abolnasser et al. (2023), EE significantly anticipates POP metrics such as financial performance and customer happiness. Similarly, Ogbonnaya and Aryee (2021) underlined the function of EE as a moderator in the interaction between HR practices and POP. These findings highlight the significance of EE in molding employees' perceptions of organizational performance, as well as its potential impact on overall organizational

success. Researchers have also investigated the role of employee well-being in the connection between employee engagement and performance. Hauff et al. (2022) successfully revealed the relationship between employee engagement and perceived organizational performance in a model where employee well-being also optimized the relation. Moreover, many recent research studies affirmed a conclusive and inevitable straight relationship between employee engagement and organizational performance (Tensay and Sing, 2020; Ahmed et al., 2020). Besides, employee engagement loosely mediated the relationship between HRM functions and organizational performance (Ahmed et al., 2020). Hence, this study assumes a relationship between employee engagement (EE) and perceived organizational performance (PEP). So, we hypothesize that,

H1: EE directly influences POP in a positive manner.

High-Performance Work System (HPWS) and POP

The performance of an entity has been intercepted as the product of the ability to perform the task and the willingness to exhibit and sustain that performance. Any entity must possess a high level of dexterity and authority over a specific task to excel at the next level. Simultaneously continuous motivation must be injected into the performer to fuel their persistence in their endeavors. HPWS is generally described as an HR structure that combines a bunch of integrated HR practices, policies, and processes that are specially designed to assist the member of the organization to acquire and sharpened up diversified skills and capabilities as well as form an environment that delivers the opportunity to participate (Jewell et al., 2022; Kooij et al., 2013). Recent studies have consistently found a link between HPWS and POP. For example, Rubio-Andrés et al. (2022) discovered that HPWS predicts POP outcomes such as employee job satisfaction and organizational financial performance. Furthermore, Dorta-Afonso et al. (2021) found that employee involvement had a moderating role in the link between HPWS and POP. In addition, Keramatiyazdi et al. (2023) have studied Iran's management field to reveal the impact of HPWS on multiple organizational performance metrics, such as financial performance, operational outcomes, and HR outcomes. The study has positively explained the relationship between HPWS and the financial and operational metrics of Iranian organizations' performance. Besides, many researchers have reported a significant impact of HPWS on organizational performance irrespective of service-providing or manufacturing organization (Ashiruet al., 2022; Ruangoon, 2015). These findings provide credibility to the hypothesis that applying effective HPWS procedures might result in increased organizational performance. Therefore, the study assumes that,

H2: HPWS favorably influences POP.

Employee Task Proficiency (ETP) and POP

Recent research is scarce on the association between Employee Task Proficiency (ETP) and Perceived Organizational Performance (POP). However, researchers have repeatedly stressed task proficiency as a significant component of individual job performance (El-Kassar et al. 2022). Few studies show a direct link between ETP and POP, but researchers have thought that employees who are better at their jobs are more likely to contribute to the overall performance and effectiveness of the organization (Klebe et al., 2021).

ETP, as a measure of employees' task performance competence, can impact the repercussions of numerous organizational aspects. Xie et al. (2021) have found task proficiency has a moderating effect on the relationship between training and employee performance. Similarly, Boon and Kalshoven (2020) discovered that task proficiency mediated the connection between High-Commitment HRM, employee engagement, and performance. These data imply that ETP acts as a major antecedent affecting POP and also as a moderator in understanding its impact on POP.

Therefore, we hypothesize that

H3: ETP has a direct positive influence on POP

H4: ETP moderates the affiliation between

- a. EE and POP*
- b. HPWS and POP*

Figure 2: Framework with Hypotheses.

Research method

Research Design and Tools

The study developed an SEM model to measure the degree of interrelations among the latent variables. The analytical portion of the study was conducted using MS Excel to explain the descriptive data and SmartPLS version 3.9 to test the hypotheses. Researchers later validated the study again using Smart PLS version 4.1.0.2. SmartPLS is considered an efficient analytical tool for SEM analysis (Ringle et al., 2024; Tirno et al., 2023; Bappy et al., 2022). The hypotheses were tested through two stages: the measurement model analysis and the path coefficient analysis. The study employed a quantitative approach for data collection. This approach collected the data using numerical values, which facilitated the SEM data analysis. The respondents were asked to rate the

particulars of the question using a Likert scale of 1-5, where 1 represented a highly unfavorable opinion and 5 represented a highly favorable opinion. The study tested the hypotheses through bias-corrected and accelerated bootstrapping with 5000 subsamples.

Variable and measurement

There were two exogenous variables (High-performance Work System- HPWS, Employee Engagement- EE), one endogenous (Perceived Organization Performance- POP), and one moderating variable (Employee Task Proficiency- ETP) used in this study. Essentially, the EE (Schaufeliet) was measured using five items. al., 2003), six items to measure HPWS (Ximenes et al., 2019), six items for POP (Carmeli et al., 2007), and three items for ETP (Griffin et al. 2017) were adopted from several prior literatures with Cronbach's alpha between 0.740 to 0.952 which are statistically reliable (Hair et al., 2019). There were 20 questions to measure the four latent variables in this study. Table 1 shows the items and their sources with respective Cronbach's alpha.

Table 1: Sources of Items

Construct	Items	Sources and Cronbach's Alpha
Employee Engagement (EE)	I am enthusiastic about my job. My job inspires me. I always persevere at work, even when things do not go well. To me, my job is challenging. I feel happy when I am working intensely.	Schaufeliet al., 2003 (0.920)
High-Performance Work System (HPWS)	Faculty members frequently participate in decision-making. University offers opportunities for training. My rewards are in line with my performance. I think my work is secure. University authority prioritizes career management. I was given the chance to advance in the position I wanted.	Ximenes et al., 2019 (0.952)
Perceived Organizational Performance (POP)	Quality of education. Ability to attract new employees for the university. Ability to retain employees. Relations between management and other employees. Financial position. Market share.	Carmeli et al., 2007 (0.740)
Employee Task Proficiency (ETP)	I always perform my core jobs properly. I always maintain standard procedures to do my job. I ensured my tasks were appropriately completed on time.	Griffin et al. 2017 (0.880)

Population and sample

According to UGC, Bangladesh 15,393 faculty members are serving in 108 private universities in Bangladesh. Among them, 4,999 teachers are female, with a ratio of 32.48% (UGC, 2021). Two hundred questionnaires were issued to gather the research data, of which 172 were collected. Due to the incomplete and inappropriate responses, 25 questionnaires were eliminated. Finally, 147 responses were used in the study, which is sufficient for the study recommended by Hair et al., 2019 as it has more than five times the total items in the survey. Many scholars suggested non-probability sampling for behavioral studies (Lehdonvirta et al., 2021; Campbell et al., 2020). The authors chose non-probability purposive sampling due to the complexity of using probability sampling for the respective population, as there is no specific faculty database on private university teachers nationwide. In addition, purposive sampling provides more flexibility, efficiency, and expert-based solutions for the sample selection (Campbell et al., 2020). The survey data was collected from 17 private universities all over the country. Among them, nine are from the Dhaka division, three from Rajshahi Division, two from the Chittagong division, two from the Khulna division, and one from the Sylhet division.

Analysis and Findings

Descriptive statistics

The study's survey was conducted on teachers working in private universities in Bangladesh. Most of the respondents, approximately 63.95%, were from the Dhaka division, as the maximum number of private universities is situated in Dhaka. Twenty two respondents were from a university in Rajshahi; five were from Sylhet, and 13 were from Chittagong and Khulna—Figure 3.

Figure 3: Location of the Respondents' University

Males comprise the most considerable portion of the group, comprising 63.27% of the total, with females for the remaining 36.73%. Regarding age, the highest share falls between the ages of 23 and 30, accounting for 60.54% of the group. Individuals aged 50 and up, on the other hand, constitute the lowest sector at 6.12%.

Table 2: Descriptive Data

Particular	Count	Percentage	Particular	Count	Percentage
Gender			Designation		
Male	93	63.27%	Lecturer	74	50.34%
Female	54	36.73%	Assistant Professor	30	20.41%
Age			Associate Professor	21	14.29%
23-30 Years	89	60.54%	Professor	22	14.97%
31-40 Years	32	21.77%	Location of the University		
41-50 Years	17	11.56%	Dhaka	94	63.95%
50+ Years	9	6.12%	Rajshahi	22	14.97%
Experience			Chittagong	13	8.84%
0-3 Years	50	34.01%	Khulna	13	8.84%
4-10 Years	71	48.30%	Sylhet	5	3.40%
11-20 Years	14	9.52%			
20+ Years	12	8.16%			

According to the survey data, approximately 82.31% of respondents have academic experience ranging from 0 to 10 years. Similarly, 70.75% of respondents are either lecturers or assistant professors.

In terms of experience, the data shows that those with 4-10 years of experience make up the majority of the group, representing 48.30% of the total sample size. Of those with more than 21 years of experience, only 8.16% of respondents have experience over 20 years. Finally, the distribution of designations shows that lecturers make up the majority (50.34%) portion of respondents, followed by assistant professors (20.41%), associate professors (14.29%), and professors (14.97%).

Assessment of the measurement model

Preliminarily, we had 20 items representing four latent variables in this study. All the loadings of the items were higher than the threshold value of 0.708, except one item from HPWS. Therefore, the item underwent removal. This removal didn't affect the analysis of the study, as up to a 20% reduction of items can be considered to run the PLS algorithm (Hair et al., 2019). Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability (CR), and average variance extracted (AVE) were applied to determine the reliability of every factor.

Cronbach's alpha is an internal consistency reliability metric that examines the degree to which items on a scale or construct are correlated with one another. Also, CR is a

reliability indicator that looks at the factor loadings of a construct's items to see how uniform it is (Hair et al., 2019). On the other hand, AVE is a convergent validity metric that compares the amount of variation collected by a concept to the measurement error (Henseler et al., 2015).

All variables exhibited great internal consistency, as reflected by Cronbach's alpha values higher than the threshold of 0.700, based on the reliability study. Similarly, the assessment of CR of each latent variable showed satisfactory results as well, with values between 0.871 and 0.928 surpassing the threshold of 0.700, showing that the framework was reliable. Furthermore, AVE indicated that the variables had appropriate convergent validity, scoring higher than the reference value of 0.500 (Hair et al., 2019).

Table 3: Measurement Model

Constructs	Items	Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Employee Engagement (EE)	EE1	0.843	0.905	0.928	0.722
	EE2	0.838			
	EE3	0.819			
	EE4	0.845			
	EE5	0.900			
High-Performance Work System (HPWS)	HPWS1	0.787	0.817	0.871	0.576
	HPWS3	0.710			
	HPWS4	0.746			
	HPWS5	0.752			
	HPWS6	0.796			
Employee Task Proficiency (ETP)	ETP1	0.841	0.819	0.892	0.733
	ETP2	0.878			
	ETP3	0.849			
Perceived Organizational Performance (POP)	POP1	0.800	0.893	0.918	0.651
	POP2	0.796			
	POP3	0.816			
	POP4	0.762			
	POP5	0.805			
	POP6	0.861			

The study calculated the heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) to assess the discriminant validity based on the survey data. Variance-based structural equation modeling uses HTMT as a technique to assess discriminant validity. To determine whether they are different from one another, it compares the correlations between several constructs. A recommended threshold value for HTMT is 0.85, where values below this threshold indicate discriminant validity (Henseler et al., 2015).

Table 4: Assessment of Discriminate validity (HTMT)

	EE	HPWS	ETP	POP
EE				
HPWS		0.585		
ETP		0.778	0.813	
POP		0.216	0.574	0.499

The correlations between the variables indicated that the HTMT of the variables is less than the reference value therefore, the survey data passed the discriminate validity test.

Hypotheses Testing

The study used the coefficient beta, standard deviation, t-value, and p-value from the study's structural model assessment to test the idea that the factors are related by using recommended bootstrapping with 5,000 samples (Ramayah et al., 2018, Hair and Alamer, 2022). Figure 3 shows the loadings of each item along with the beta value. The value in the inner circle of the endogenous variable POP indicates the adjusted R square that elucidates that the independent variables in the study can explain 42.2% of variations of the dependent variable POP, which is quite good considering behavioral research (Ozili, 2023).

Figure 3: Structural Model

In the beginning, there were five hypotheses under four primary hypotheses. The path analysis confirms three out of five hypotheses and rejected the remaining two. **Table 5** illustrates the results of the direct association between the latent variables.

Table 5: Path analysis

Hypotheses	Path	Beta	Standard Error	t-statistics	Result
H1	EE -> POP ^{NS}	-0.176	0.094	1.863	Rejected
H2	HPWS -> POP ^{***}	0.375	0.083	4.521	Accepted
H3	ETP -> POP ^{**}	0.302	0.103	2.941	Accepted
H4a	ETP*EE -> POP ^{***}	0.403	0.086	4.690	Accepted
H4b	ETP*HPWS -> POP ^{NS}	-0.016	0.080	0.197	Rejected

The study hypothesized that EE has a positive influence on the POP. The analysis of the survey data demonstrates that there is no association between EE and POP (H1: B = -0.176, t = 1.863, P=0.061). On the other hand, HPWS found to have a direct positive impact on the POP which confirms the second hypothesis of the study (H2: B= 0.375, t= 4.521, P= 0.000). ETP has also a direct positive effect on POP with a beta value of 0.302, t value of 2.941, and p value of 0.004 which confirms third hypothesis of the study.

The study also tried to find out how ETP affected the link between EE and POP and HPWS and POP in the fourth hypothesis. The results show that ETP did not help the connection between HPWS and POP (H4a: B = -0.016, t = 0.080, P = 0.836), but it did help the connection between EE and POP (H4b: B = 0.403, t = 0.086, P = 0.000). Therefore, this study can conclude that while EE does not impact organizational performance, ETP can help EE enhance the POP. On the contrary, though HPWS has a significant favorable influence on POP, ETP cannot play any role in boosting organizational performance by intervening in the relationship, which rejects the fourth hypothesis partially.

Discussions

The research results give us a lot of information about how employee engagement (EE), high-performance work systems (HPWS), employee task proficiency (ETP), and perceived organizational performance (POP) are related. The hypotheses that have been accepted (H2, H3, and H4a) describe how HPWS, ETP, and the way that ETP and EE affect POP. However, the rejected hypotheses (H1 and H4b) highlight the need for further research and a deeper understanding of the underlying mechanisms.

The fact that H2 was accepted backs up earlier research that showed how adding HPWS to POP had positive effects. Prior studies reinforce the idea that fostering a high-performance work environment improves POP. It seems that companies that have HR policies like letting employees participate in decisions, giving rewards based on performance, and allowing employees to keep learning are more likely to have better organizational performance (Park et al., 2023; Ashiru et al., 2022). The widespread acceptance of H3 lends credence to the idea that ETP is a primary determinant of POP. Organizations should prioritize the growth and retention of skilled workers through training, development programs, and continuous performance evaluation.

Previous evidence supports the uptake of H3, suggesting a positive correlation between ETP and POP. Tang and Vandenberghe (2022) discovered that ETP positively influenced organizational performance in the healthcare sector. Another study, by Probst et al. (2017), found that employee task proficiency influenced perceived organizational success considerably. These findings highlight the significance of training and retaining talented staff in order to increase organizational performance.

Nevertheless, the denial of H1 demonstrates that the direct connection between EE and POP is not as significant as initially expected. While employee involvement is commonly acknowledged to be an important determinant of organizational success (Yadav et al., 2022; Heslina and Syahrini (2021), the data imply that it may not have a direct impact on POP. In their Indonesian study on MNC employees, Sungmala and Verawat (2021) also found contrary evidence. This investigation showed that employee engagement doesn't have any direct influence on POP. In general, teachers tend to have a high moral position, which motivates them to serve the organization in a better way even though they might not be given any opportunity to be involved in the complex decision-making of the universities (Asif et al., 2020). Moreover, the decision-makers in private universities tend to be experienced academicians who always focus on academic integrity and the interests of the faculty members, which also allows the faculty members to invest their valuable time and effort in other personal development in the field of research and innovation. This result also aligns with what Albrecht et al. (2015) found in their study. They discovered that while EE had a positive relationship with some organizational outcomes, it became less strong when it came to objective performance. This outcome suggests that employee engagement may have a more indirect influence on POP.

H4a highlighted the synergistic effect of task proficiency and engagement on POP. The study suggests that EE doesn't have any direct influence on the POP. Employees who have high ETP and are highly engaged in their work are more likely to contribute significantly to the organization's overall performance. This study outcome emphasizes the significance of considering employee skills and involvement levels when developing human resource practices and regulations. Close to the study, Boon and Kalshoven (2014) researched the moderating effect of ETP on the linkage between HPWS and employee engagement. They found full moderation between them.

According to H4b, the interplay between ETP and HPWS has no discernible impact on POP. This finding contradicts earlier studies that claimed task proficiency and a supportive work environment had a combined influence on performance outcomes. For example, Fragoso et al. (2022) discovered that employee abilities and a supportive work environment jointly improved work outcomes. This disparity could be related to contextual factors and requires deeper investigation.

Conclusions and Recommendations

This study attempted to explore the connections between employee engagement (EE), high-performance work systems (HPWS), employee task proficiency (ETP), and perceived organizational performance (POP). The results support the hypothesis that HPWS and ETP have a direct favorable impact on POP. However, the hypothesis indicating that EE has a direct favorable effect on POP was not supported. Also, the fact

that ETP was created to control the connection between EE and POP shows that ETP can change how EE affects the performance of an organization. Surprisingly, ETP did not affect the connection between HPWS and POP. These findings highlight the significance of creating high-performance work processes and cultivating ETP in businesses to increase POP. The findings also indicate that the direct impact of EE on organizational success may be less substantial. Instead, the study focuses on the indirect effects of high employee engagement via task performance.

Additional research is commendable for generating further information on the underlying paradigm. Furthermore, contextual circumstances can alter the research findings so that future research avenues can be reopened. Even so, future research can investigate other HRM factors in varied industrial and organizational contexts to validate the findings.

Notably, this study contributes to the current literature on employee engagement, high-performance work systems, and organizational performance and also presents significant insights to HR practitioners and scholars. Similarly, the study result will help business owners boost productivity by purposefully coordinating HPWS with other efforts to improve employees' task proficiency within the company. Hence, organizations should prioritize HPWS parallel to strategic goals and objectives. This includes reforming HR policies and practices that encourage employee participation, performance-based awards, and chances for continuing development.

Moreover, owners should analyze and update the HPWS regularly to ensure a successful relevant dive 's performance. Furthermore, firms should invest in ETP through training, development programs, and comprehensive performance evaluation. Organizations can lift their performance by providing employees with the essential skills and knowledge to perform their responsibilities effectively. To facilitate the aforementioned aspects, identifying skill gaps, developing targeted training programs, and providing staff with ongoing support and feedback can be influential and beneficial.

Theoretical and Practical Implications

This study suggests HPWS has a direct positive impact on POP, which is consistent with previous studies emphasizing the necessity of creating a supportive and performance-driven work environment. This strengthens the theoretical foundations of HPWS and its influence on the performance of the organization. On the other hand, the strong correlation between ETP and POP emphasizes the importance of employee skills and competencies in driving organizational success. This study lends credence to the premise that firms should spend on training and development programs to increase employee task proficiency and, as a result, overall performance. The findings of this research have practical relevance as well for the businesses looking to improve their performance and effectiveness. Organizations should comprehend the significance of EE and its relationship to task performance. While employee involvement may not have a direct impact on perceived organizational success, when combined with high levels of task proficiency, it can play a critical role. To optimize their impact on organizational performance, businesses should focus on cultivating both employee engagement and task proficiency.

Limitations and Future Implications

The study was carried out at private universities in Bangladesh, which may limit the findings' applicability to other universities or regions. Organizational dynamics, cultural variations, and contextual variances can all have a substantial impact on the interactions between the variables under consideration. Therefore, we should exercise caution when applying these findings to different organizational situations. The study relied on self-reported data collected through questionnaires, which could be influenced by common method bias and social desirability bias. Factors such as participants' expectations or social desires could have influenced their replies, leading to data biases. To overcome these constraints and provide more comprehensive knowledge of the links, future studies should try merging alternative data collection methods and sources.

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